

Comparative Evaluation of Three Different Mechanical Properties of Four Orthodontic Wires By Instrumented Indentation Technique (IIT)-an In Vitro Study.

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Abstract

Background- Brackets, molar tubes, and orthodontic wires work together to exert stresses on the teeth as therapy progresses. Because they are so intrinsic to the efficacy of orthodontic treatment, the mechanical properties of orthodontic wires are very important.

AIM- The researchers set out to compare the mechanical qualities of conventional round orthodontic wires (i.e. NiTi, TMA, HANT & Gummetal, that are used in the treatment during the initial stage of levelling and aligning.

Method- The study was conducted in the Nanoindenter Facility in the Department of Metallurgical Engineering & Material Science of Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay. The machinery used to perform the indentation and scratch test to determine the characteristics of the arch wire was Hysitron TI Premier Nano indenter, BrukerTM

Result- Post Hoc test was done for individual comparison for hardness and significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$ between the four wires i.e. HANT, NiTi, TMA, Gummetal. The mean values of the Vickers hardness(HVIT), modulus of elasticity(Es) and coefficient of friction of the HANT, NiTi, TMA, and Gummetal were compared using a one-way ANOVA test, the results were found to be significant at $p \leq 0.05$, which meant that there was a significant difference

Conclusion- The average coefficient of friction for Gummetal is lower than TMA while it is significantly much higher than HANT and NiTi.

Keywords- Efficacy, Orthodontic Treatment, Nickel Titanium, Heat Activated Nickel Titanium, Titanium Molybdenum Alloy, Gummetal

Introduction

Orthodontic therapy relies on arch wires. Through the use of molar tubes and brackets, they produce the necessary stresses to shift the teeth into place. Different archwires are available with different cross-sections. As the orthodontic wires, brackets, and molar tubes work together, they exert stresses on the teeth. The characteristics of a perfect archwire are defined by the following criteria:

- (1) High formability
- (2) low stiffness
- (3) high range, and
- (4) high strength

The material must also have the capacity to be weldable and solderable. Not only that, but the material also needs to be affordable. No orthodontic archwire material has been able to meet all of these criteria. To get the greatest results, use a different archwire for each function.¹

Arch wires are utilized in fixed ortho-

dontic appliance therapy to provide force to the teeth. The effectiveness of the multistage treatment process depends on the careful selection of arch wires. No fixed appliance treatment phase is best served by a single archwire. Typically used to address crowding and small tooth rotations, the initial archwire is the first archwire put into the permanent appliance at the start of therapy. People generally agree that optimal forces light, continuous forces are the best way to move teeth in a controlled and predictable way while causing little damage to the teeth and their supporting tissues²

The mechanical qualities of the wires are crucial to the effectiveness of orthodontic therapy. The modulus of elasticity, yield strength, fracture strength, and other basic mechanical parameters are often evaluated

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by means of tensile, bending, and torsion tests.³

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) has acknowledged instrumented indentation testing (IIT) as a new alternative method for assessing several mechanical properties, including as hardness, modulus of elasticity, creep, relaxation, and more.^{4,5}

Indentation testing with a precisely shaped and force-controlled probe is a common method for studying the mechanical characteristics, including elastic stiffness and hardness, of solid-state materials. As the indenter is inserted and removed from the surface material, the device's high-resolution capacitive gauges and actuators allow it to continuously adjust and monitor the load and displacement.⁶

For the purposes of this experiment, the following definition of the properties of the archwires that will be determined is mentioned below.⁷

1. The ratio of stress to strain inside the elastic limit is known as the elastic modulus (E) and is measured in pounds/inches. This is another name for Young's Modulus.
2. Difficulty with localized plastic deformation caused by mechanical indentation or abrasion is measured by hardness (H).
3. term is the coefficient of friction, which is the ratio of the normal force acting on two surfaces to the frictional force that is opposing their motion.

Method

The Nano indenter Facility at the Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay's Department of Metallurgical Engineering & Material Science was the site of the research.

The types of arch wires used as the samples for this study are mentioned in (table.1) with their product/code, manufacturer, cross-section, and composition in weight percentage, diameter and length.

Product/Code	Manufacturer	Cross-section	Type	Composition	Diameter	Length
SE NiTi Trueform™	G&H orthodontics	Round	Conventional super elastic NiTi	Ni% 54.52 Ti% 45.48	0.016inch	20mm
CNA Beta 3 Global	Liberal Traders Pvt.Ltd.	Round	TMA	Ti% 79 Mo% 11 Zr% 6 Sn% 4	0.016inch	20mm
Gummetal®	J.Morita Europe GMBH	Round	TiNb	Ti% 23 Nb% 0.7 Ta% 2 Zr% 1.20	0.016inch	20mm
Niti Thermal Trueform	Liberal Traders Pvt.Ltd.	Round	HANT	Ni% 55 Ti% 45	0.016inch	20mm

Table:1 commercial name, product/code, manufacturer, cross-section, Type, composition in weight percentage, diameter and length of as received pre-formed orthodontic archwires used in this study

For precision sectioning of the archwire we used a low-speed oil-cooled diamond saw machine by(IsoMet, Buehler, Lake Bluff,Il). The machinery used to perform the indentation and scratch test to determine the characteristics of the archwire was Hysitron TI Premier Nano indenter, Bruker™.

Specimen preparation: Table :”1 lists all of the orthodontic archwires that were part of this study, together

with their manufacturer codes, cross-sections, commercial names, and weight percentages, diameters, and lengths. A 10-millimeter-long portion was meticulously cut out of each wire sample using a cutting tool (IsoMet, Buehler, Lake Bluff, Il.). The next step was to mount the samples longitudinally in epoxy resin and polish them using normal metallographic methods. After that, they were vibratory polished for 12 hours in a solution of 0.5 µm colloidal silica. The goal was to make sure the surface wasn't too rough.”

Nanoindentation and Nano scratch measurements: “A material's "mechanical fingerprint" in response to contact deformation can be obtained by analyzing nanoindentation load-displacement curves. Using a pointed trigonal (Berkovich) indenter, one may obtain both the Young's modulus and the indentation hardness number. To understand the relationship between the indenter displacement, δ , and the applied load, P, the equation $P = Km\delta^2$ may be utilized for several materials. The Km of a material may be predicted from its hardness (H) and Young's modulus (E). As a result, if we know E, we can use the experimental loading curve to find H. In cases when analyzing unloading curves is not feasible, this approach provides a feasible alternative to finite element modelling as an easily applied methodology. Nano scratch and nano indentation experiments were conducted using the Hysitron TI Premier Nano indenter, which is produced by Bruker™. We used a load-controlled setting to do the indentation tests. The durations of loading (10 seconds), holding (5 seconds), and emptying (8 mN), in that order, were recorded. A diamond Berkovich probe with a tip radius of 200 nm was used for the studies. Ten indentations were made on each specimen, and the parameters were averaged. It We recorded all force-indentation depth curves according to the ISO 14577-1 standard, and then we calculated the indentation hardness (HIT), indentation modulus (EIT), and percentage of the elastic component of indentation work (η IT), which is also called the elastic index.”

To assess the wear resistance of the wire Nanoscratch measurements were performed to determine the dynamic friction co-efficient of the material which is a measure of its wear resistance. 5 constant load scratches at 8mN load, each 5 µm in length were performed on each specimen. The diamond Berkovich probe used in these experiments scratches the surface of the specimens at 8mN load for a lateral distance of 5 µm, and quantities like normal load and displacement, lateral load, and displacement are recorded. The co-efficient of friction is found as the ratio between lateral force and normal force. Data from the scratch segments were extracted and analysed. The coefficient of friction for all the scratch segments of each specimen were averaged to determine its coefficient of friction value.

Result

Based on the nanoindentation and nano scratch test performed by Hysitron TI Premier Nano indenter, Bruker™ results were derived by implementing the formulas by Oliver-Pharr as stated in the methodology the Vickers Hardness and modulus of elasticity were derived. The mean value of Vickers

Hardness (HVIT) of the sample wires i.e. HANT, NiTi, TMA, Gummetal

- HANT- “the mean hardness(HVIT) = 3.00Gpa with standard deviation ± 0.12 Gpa”
- NiTi-“the mean hardness(HVIT) =2.64Gpa with standard deviation 0.08Gpa”
- TMA-“the mean hardness(HVIT) =2.81Gpa with standard deviation of 0.09Gpa”
- Gummetal-“the mean hardness(HVIT) =0.08Gpa with standard deviation of 0.18Gpa”

The mean hardness(HVIT) was noted to be highest for HANT at mean value of 3.00Gpa with a standard deviation of ± 0.12 Gpa. and lowest hardness(HVIT) for Gummetal with the mean reading of 0.84Gpa and standard deviation of ± 0.18 Gpa (table-2). The mean value of modulus of elasticity (Es) the sample wires i.e. HANT, NiTi, TMA, Gummetal

- HANT- the mean modulus of elasticity (Es)=36.27Gpa with standard deviation of 1.14Gpa
- NiTi-the mean - the mean modulus of elasticity (Es)=38.47Gpa with standard deviation of 2.66Gpa
- TMA-the mean modulus of elasticity (Es)=67.82Gpa with standard deviation of 1.59Gpa.
- Gummetal-the mean modulus of elasticity (Es)=21.43Gpa with standard deviation of 2.21Gpa

The mean modulus of elasticity(Es) was noted to be highest for TMA at the mean value of 67.82Gpa with a standard deviation of ± 1.59 Gpa and the lowest mean modulus of elasticity was for Gummetal with a mean reading of 21.43Gpa and standard deviation of ± 2.21 Gpa. For the nano scratch results of HANT, Ni-Ti, TMA and Gum metal, there is variation in co-efficient of friction as a function of the lateral displacement for all the specimens. While Gum metal and TMA showed large variation in co-efficient of friction, where as Ni-Ti and HANT, have nominally constant values.

- HANT-the mean coefficient of friction =0.24 with a standard deviation of 0.12
- NiTi-the mean coefficient of friction=0.29 with a standard deviation of 0.13
- TMA-the mean coefficient of friction =0.42 with a standard deviation of 0.19
- Gummetal- the mean coefficient of friction =0.40 with a standard deviation of 0.19. HANT shows the lowest average coefficient of friction (0.24 ± 0.12), while TMA shows the highest (0.42 ± 0.19).

Gum metal also shows a coefficient of friction of (0.40 ± 0.19). The test readings were statistically analyzed to determine the hardness, modulus of elasticity, and coefficient of friction by ANOVA and Post Hoc Tests

The mean values of the vickers hardness(HVIT) ,modulus of elasticity(Es) and coefficient of friction were compared using a one-way ANOVA test , the results were found to be significant at $p \leq 0.05$.Post Hoc test was done for individual comparison for hardness and significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$ between the four wires

Post Hoc Test				
Dependent Variable			Mean Difference	Sig.
HVIT	HANT	NiTi	0.36	0.000
		TMA	0.19	0.004
		Gummetal	2.17	0.000
	NiTi	HANT	-0.36	0.000
		TMA	-0.17	0.017
		Gummetal	1.80	0.000
	TMA	HANT	-0.19	0.004
		NiTi	0.17	0.017
		Gummetal	1.97	0.000
	Gummetal	HANT	-2.17	0.000
		NiTi	-1.80	0.000
		TMA	-1.97	0.000

Table:2

Post Hoc Test				
Dependent Variable			Mean Difference	Sig.
Es(elastic modulus)	HANT	NiTi	-2.20	0.052
		TMA	-31.55	0.000
		Gummetal	14.83	0.000
	NiTi	HANT	2.20	0.052
		TMA	-29.35	0.000
		Gummetal	17.03	0.000
	TMA	HANT	31.55	0.000
		NiTi	29.35	0.000
		Gummetal	46.38	0.000
	Gummetal	HANT	-14.83	0.000
		NiTi	-17.03	0.000
		TMA	-46.38	0.000

Table 3

Post Hoc test was done for individual comparison for elastic modulus and significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$ between the four wires i.e. HANT, NiTi, TMA, Gummetal .

Post Hoc Test				
Dependent Variable			Mean Difference	Sig.
Co-Efficient of Friction	HANT	NiTi	-0.05	0.000
		TMA	-0.19	0.000
		Gummetal	-0.16	0.000
	NiTi	HANT	0.05	0.000
		TMA	-0.14	0.000
		Gummetal	-0.11	0.000
	TMA	HANT	0.19	0.000
		NiTi	0.14	0.000
		Gummetal	0.02	0.000
	Gummetal	HANT	0.16	0.000
		NiTi	0.11	0.000
		TMA	-0.02	0.000

Table 4

Discussion

Orthodontic therapy begins with the archwire. With the use of brackets and molar tubes, archwires may shift teeth and provide mandatory forces. Numerous cross-sections of archwires are available. Forces are applied by the interaction of wires with orthodontic brackets and molar tubes.

Orthodontists get three-dimensional control over tooth movement during the active phase of treatment by using archwires in multibracket appliances. Because the elastic orthodontic wire applies the required force, teeth may be moved with braces. Its Young Modulus and comparable strength made it the preferred material, soon replacing the more expensive gold-nickel wire. Orthodontia has long made use of wires made of stainless steel (SS) or cobalt chrome (CoCr).

The next phase of orthodontics was inaugurated with nickel-titanium (NiTi) wire in the 1970s. Orthodontic treatment's early phase was made simpler by the material's superelasticity and shape memory. The middle and end stages of orthodontic treatment should not use it since it is nearly hard to bend. Moreover, the 50% nickel content of NiTi alloy may cause an allergic reaction by prompting the body to generate antibodies. Orthodontic wires should not contain any heavy metals, as intended.

For high-stress medical applications like orthodontic and

orthopaedic implants and orthodontic wires, the most important and subsequent category of nickel- and chromium-free alloys is beta-titanium (-Ti) alloys. Orthodontists now have access to titanium-molybdenum (TiMo) wires that are bendable and exhibit properties comparable to CoCr and NiTi alloys. -Ti wires can be used in place of CoCr and SS wires, however they aren't quite as adaptable for uses that call for NiTi alloys.

Finding the perfect orthodontic wire will take more time. For metals and alloys to be suitable for use in biomedicine, they must meet certain criteria, including being biocompatible, non-toxic, and corrosion resistant. In addition to having a high tensile strength, an ideal orthodontic archwire would also be visually beautiful, very elastic, pliable, and easy to bend. For optimal tooth movement, it's also important that the orthodontic force be easily adjustable and that the coefficient of friction be low.

In 2001, Toyota Central RandD, Inc. in Japan created Gummetal, a novel β -Ti alloy with many functionalities. The Metallurgical Research Department. Oxygen, zirconium, tantalum, niobium, and titanium make it up. According to the theory of atomic valence, gum metal's chemical formula is $Ti_{23}Nb_{0.7}Ta_{2}Zr_{1.2}O$. To achieve its primary characteristics, this alloy is subjected to extensive cold working. so is quite unusual for an alloy to possess both high strength and very high malleability simultaneously, yet this non-toxic alloy manages to do so with a very low value of Young's modulus, according to the manufacturers. The special quality of this new alloy, according to the producers, is the perfect control over plastic deformation, also known as crystal displacement.¹⁰

Hasegawa65 claims that gummetal is practically perfect for use as an orthodontic archwire. Initially, this should cause the obstruction to be processed with a little continuous force. Gummetal can decrease orthodontic force even with big tooth movements since it does not follow Hooke's Law.

This study aimed to evaluate the hardness, modulus of elasticity, and surface roughness (i.e. coefficient of friction) of a novel γ -Ti archwire (gummetal) by conducting nanoindentation and nano scratch tests, and then comparing the results with those of NiTi, HANT, and TMA that were of comparable size and cross-section.

The Bruker™ Hysitron TI Premier Nano indenter was used to perform the nanoscratch and nanoindentation experiments. By pressing an indenter into a material's surface and then photographing the resulting imprint, the indentation technique may be utilized to evaluate the material's mechanical characteristics. Initially, the hardness could be ascertained by means of the indentation test. The examined material is pressed into form using a hard, precisely sized device called an indenter, and then released. The connection between total indentation load and displacement or area allows one to calculate the hardness of the tested material.

We conducted the indentation testing in a loadcontrolled environment. A loading duration of 10 seconds, a holding time of 5 seconds, and an unloading time of 10 seconds were utilized, with a maximum load of 8 mN. The investigations

were conducted using a 200 nm tip radius diamond Berkovich probe. We averaged the parameters measured from 10 indents on each specimen, which included SE NiTi TrueformTM, CNA Beta 3 Global, Gummetal^R, and Niti Thermal Trueform. Oliver-Pharr determined the hardness and elastic modulus using the following formulas.

Coefficient of friction, hardness (HVIT), and elastic modulus (Es) were calculated using the given formulae.

Examining the nanoindentation-based elastic moduli (Es) of each wire.

The findings demonstrated that TMA had the greatest mean elastic modulus at 67.82 Gpa with a standard deviation (SD) of 1.59 Gpa, compared to gummetal's lowest value of 21.43 Gpa and SD of 2.21 Gpa. Results from a comparable study by Laino et al. (2012) and Murakami et al. (2015) using a 3-point bending test showed that gummetal had the lowest elastic modulus and TMA had the highest. Our findings corroborated their findings.

Evaluation of All Wires' Hardness (HVIT) via Nanoindentation

With a mean hardness of 0.84Gpa and a standard deviation of 0.018Gpa, gummetal produced the softest material compared to HANT, NiTi, and TMA. Similar studies were conducted by Zinelis.S et.al.⁵⁸ Murakami et al., and Suzuki et al.^{14,15} where they evaluated the bending strength of Gummetal, TMA & Niti they concluded in their study that gummetal showed the lowest stiffness, followed by NiTi, and TMA wire showed to be the hardest as compared to the other two wires, the present study shows similar outcome, though the method of testing done by Murakami et al., and Suzuki et al.^{14,15} was different from that of nanoindentation test the outcome of the results was same but with different values, while Zinelis.S et.al.⁹ used similar indentation method in their study using TMA and NiTi wires, the results of this study were in agreement with the results of their study stating hardness of TMA being more than NiTi.

Comparison of the coefficient of friction of all the wires in this study.

HANT showed the lowest coefficient of friction with mean 0.24 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.12, followed by NiTi with mean of 0.29 and SD of 0.13, with Gummetal showing a higher coefficient of friction when compared to NiTi and HANT with mean 0.40 and SD of 0.19 while TMA showed the highest amongst all with mean 0.42 and SD of 0.19. the coefficient of friction of given wires in this study was determined between the diamond Berkovich probe used in Hysitron TI Premier Nano indenter, BrukerTM while most of the studies for the coefficient of friction carried out by others were between the orthodontic archwires and several orthodontic bracket systems. A study done by Megumi Tagada et.al.⁸ in 2018 determined frictional force (FF) NiTi, TMA & Gummetal(TiNb) and found that the FF of TMA was the highest in relation to the stainless steel bracket system.

Abdullah Albawardi et.al.¹⁶ in 2022 compared the coefficient of friction of Gummetal, TMA, SS, and rhodium-plated aesthetic Gummetal(E-GM) they observed that TMA

archwire produced the highest coefficient of friction when compared with other wires.

Schmeidl K et.al.⁶² in the year 2021 evaluated the frictional properties of Gummetal (TiNb), nickel-titanium NiTi, and Titanium-molybdenum (TiMo) they found that TiMo showed the highest friction force but Gummetal showed similar frictional resistance as NiTi. The results obtained by present study, the friction force of TMA was greater than Gummetal, is in accordance with the results obtained by previous researchers Megumi Tagada et.al.⁸, Abdullah Albawardi et.al.¹⁶

Conclusion

On the basis of the data derived from this study, it was found that the average coefficient of friction for Gummetal is lower than TMA while it is significantly much higher than HANT and NiTi.

Such an ability of the material makes it a good candidate for orthodontic wires during leveling and aligning stage i.e. the initial phase of the fixed orthodontic treatment only in scenarios where the patient is allergic to nickel and conventional NiTi or HANT wires can't be used and can be a good replacement of TMA since the coefficient of friction of the gummetal is much lower than that of TMA.

However further research needs to be done on this particular property of the wire, friction is orthodontic remains for open debate. The current methodology employed in the study for friction is inadequate and does not simulate the oral environment. So only improved methodology and further study can shed more light on the topic

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